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CLEWs-Based Insights for India's Sustainable Development Pathways

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Executive Summary

India's economic growth, population, and urbanization are intensifying pressures on energy, land, and water resources. Using the CLEWs framework within OSeMOSYS, this study assessed three scenarios: Business as Usual (BAU), No Biofuel, and Net Zero, to evaluate sustainable development pathways. The BAU scenario reveals continued reliance on coal, with emissions peaking around 2048-2050 and extensive forest-to-cropland conversion, threatening both climate and food security. The No Biofuel pathway reduces land-use conflicts but shifts dependence toward nuclear power. The Net Zero scenario demonstrates that deep decarbonization is feasible by 2070, with emissions nearing zero by 2055 through accelerated deployment of nuclear, solar, and wind energy. However, this pathway requires 18.42% higher annual investment compared to BAU.

The analysis highlights that India must integrate energy, land, and water planning to ensure a resilient transition. Actionable steps include scaling up clean energy technologies; particularly nuclear, solar, and wind, limiting large-scale biofuel expansion to protect food security, and improving irrigation efficiency. Additionally, robust climate financing mechanisms are essential to meet the higher investment needs of a net-zero pathway. These measures will enable India to balance development with sustainability and advance towards its 2070 climate commitments.

1. Introduction

Rapid economic growth, industrialization, and urbanization are driving a surge in energy demand, projected to double by 2040 under current policies (IEA, 2021). Coal dominates electricity generation, contributing over 70% of output (IEA, 2024), while renewable energy capacity has surpassed 180 GW by 2023 (IRENA, 2024). As the third-largest global energy consumer and the second-largest in Asia, India plays a pivotal role in regional and global energy futures.

India's socio-economic and environmental context adds complexity to its energy transition. Agriculture employs 42% of the workforce (FAO, 2023) and consumes over 80% of freshwater withdrawals (FAO AQUASTAT, 2022), creating intense pressure on land and water systems. Rapid urbanization, industrial expansion, and land-use changes have increased competition for land between food production, bioenergy crops, and renewable energy infrastructure. Water scarcity is exacerbated in several regions due to over-extraction for irrigation and energy cooling. The energy sector accounts for nearly 75% of national GHG emissions (UNFCCC, 2022), while India remains highly vulnerable to climate impacts, including heatwaves, erratic monsoons, and floods (IPCC, 2023).

This study applies the CLEWs framework (Climate-Land-Energy-Water Systems) within OSeMOSYS (MUIO 5.3) to capture these interdependencies in India's context. By integrating energy system modelling with land and water constraints, the framework examines how transitions in power technologies, biofuel deployment, and water-efficient practices affect emissions, land allocation, and system costs. Three scenarios: Baseline, No Biofuel, and Net zero, these are assessed to understand trade-offs, quantify cross-sector impacts, and provide actionable insights for policymakers, supporting India's sustainable energy transition and its net-zero emissions target by 2070.

2. Methodology

This study employs the Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems (CLEWs) framework integrated with the Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) to analyze India's energy system transitions. OSeMOSYS is the underlying code for the analysis, it is a demand-led, bottom-up optimization model that minimizes system costs while satisfying energy demand. The model operates by optimizing technology choices under defined constraints, making it suitable for long-term scenario analysis and cross-sector resource planning (Howells et al., 2011; Ramos et al., 2022).

The Starter Data Kit (SDK) within OSeMOSYS provided the baseline representation of India's energy system, incorporating reference assumptions from Barnes et al. (2022). Agricultural and water system data were sourced from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and International Energy Agency (IEA) databases.

Technology options included in the model are as follows:

Energy (Power sector): Coal-fired power plants, natural gas plants, oil-based generation, nuclear power, hydropower, wind, solar, biomass power.

Land use and agriculture: Food crops (rice, wheat), bioenergy crops (sugarcane), forest land, urban/built-up land and other land categories. These land-use options were linked

to water demand for irrigation and to biomass/energy production potential, ensuring representation of cross-sector trade-offs.

Three scenarios were modelled:

Figure 1 Representation of three Scenarios

3. Results

This modelling exercise explored the following research results:

In Business as Usual (BAU) Scenario:

Figure 2 shows a steady increase in India's energy production during the optimization period from 2023 to 2055, driven by a GDP growth of 6.04%. The dominant share of energy comes from coal, which shows gradual increases throughout the period. Solar and wind energy grow more noticeably after 2035, suggesting a slow but steady diversification of the energy mix. Nuclear and natural gas remain small contributors, while biomass is very marginal.

Figure 2 Power Plant Production

Figure 3, is for a visualisation of crop demand during the model period and indicates a consistent and steady increase in crop production over time, from 2020 to 2055. This rise in production is primarily driven by the demand resulting from a population growth of 0.89%.

Figure 3 Crop Production

Figure 4 shows that in the BAU scenario, the dominant land use in India is the cultivation of crops, and it increases steadily between the calibration period of 2020-2023 to 2033. A key inference is that to meet the rising crop demand, forest land is entirely replaced by cropland by 2033. The model also slowly converts rainfed land into irrigated land to meet the crop demand after crop land expansion is saturated.

Figure 4 Land Use

Figure 5, illustrates the shift in agricultural practices within the BAU scenario. It shows that irrigated land initially declines as rainfed crops increase. However, after 2033, when rainfed land can no longer be expanded, the model begins to transform rainfed land into irrigated land to continue meeting crop demand

Figure 5 Rainfed vs Irrigated Crops

Comparison of Power Plant Production for three Scenarios, Figure 6:

- In **Business as Usual (BAU)** scenario, energy production in India grows steadily from 2020 to 2055, driven by an average GDP growth of 6.04%. The dominant share of energy comes from coal, which shows gradual increases, while solar and wind power grow more noticeably after 2035.
- In **No biofuel** scenario, it demonstrates a slight increase in overall energy demand production due to the introduction of electric vehicles (EVs). This change is significant enough for the model to suggest a radical shift in technology choice, promoting nuclear power over oil.
- In the **Net Zero** scenario, model suggests a radical change in technology choices, with nuclear power being promoted over solar energy.

Figure 6 Power Generation in three scenarios

Comparison of Annual Emissions for BAU and Net Zero:

Figure 7 compares greenhouse gas emissions between the BAU and Net Zero scenarios. In the BAU scenario, emissions continue to rise steadily, peaking around 2048–2050.

Conversely, in the Net Zero scenario, coal emissions drop drastically after 2025. The overall emissions steadily decrease, nearing zero by 2055, indicating a successful pathway to decarbonization, for India to achieve Net Zero by 2070.

Figure 7 Annual Emission Comparison

Comparison of Annual Investment for BAU and Net Zero:

Figure 8 shows the annual investment required for the Net Zero pathway is 18.42% more than the investment needed for the Business as Usual (BAU) scenario. This increased cost is a key financial implication of transitioning to a sustainable energy system. It highlights that achieving a net-zero future requires significant financial commitment.

Figure 8 Annual Investment Comparison

5. Discussion

This analysis of India's development pathways reveals several critical insights and implications for the country's sustainable future. The core finding is that achieving India's climate goals requires an integrated approach to managing energy, land, and water resources. The Business as Usual (BAU) scenario, which shows continued reliance on coal and a steady increase in emissions peaking around 2048-2050, is not a viable long-term solution. The unchecked expansion of biofuel and the resulting water stress and land-use conflicts threaten food security.

The analysis of alternative scenarios provides a clear direction for policy. The **Net Zero scenario** demonstrates that a radical change in technology choices is necessary to achieve decarbonization. Specifically, the model promotes a shift towards **nuclear power over solar** as the cost optimal solution to help decrease emissions, which drop drastically after 2025 and near zero by 2055. The **No Biofuel scenario** also highlights a potential pathway by showing that removing biofuel demand could lead to a shift toward nuclear power over oil and help preserve forest land.

These findings have direct implications for policy. The study recommends scaling up nuclear, solar, and wind energy with efficient irrigation and integrated land-use planning. This is crucial for ensuring energy security and meeting net zero commitments while minimizing water usage. Furthermore, the significant financial cost of the Net Zero pathway, requiring an **18.42% increase in annual investment** compared to BAU underscores the need to prepare a dedicated climate financing plan.

Limitations and Future Research

The study acknowledges several limitations and outlines key areas for future research. One avenue for future research is to model climate shocks such as heatwaves and monsoon variability as scenarios which are crucial for understanding India's environmental vulnerabilities from a nexus perspective. In terms of limitations, including more granular state-level water and crop data would enhance the model's accuracy and provide more specific optimization pathways. This would help to address implementation challenges and better inform interventions at a local level.

7. Conclusion

Based on the analysis of the presented scenarios, India's sustainable development hinges on a fundamental shift away from its business-as-usual practices. The current reliance on coal-based energy and land use that encroaches on forests to meet agricultural demand is unsustainable and threatens the country's climate and food security goals. The model shows that a Net Zero pathway is feasible, but it requires radical changes in technology choices and significant financial investment.

Recommendations

To achieve its climate commitments, India must implement a multi-faceted strategy that integrates energy, land, and water management.

1. **Scale Up Clean Energy:** There must be a concerted effort to scale up the adoption of nuclear, solar, and wind energy. The model suggests promoting nuclear power over solar to drastically reduce coal emissions.
2. **Invest in Efficiency:** Implement efficient irrigation and integrated land-use planning to ensure energy security and meet climate goals while minimizing water use.
3. **Secure Climate Financing:** The Net Zero pathway is projected to cost 18.42% more in annual investment than the BAU scenario. Therefore, a robust climate financing plan is essential to accommodate this increased investment.

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